

Appendix C: NIRSpec spectra

In Figs. C.1 and C.2 we show the NIRSpec prism spectra used for obtaining our updated multiple image catalog. The reduction and redshift extraction is outlined in Sect. 2.3. In the following, we describe two cases where `msaexp` fitting with wide redshift prior did not produce satisfying results. In the spectrum of K82.2 we find a noticeable emission line consistent with [OIII] emission in K82.1 grism spectrum (Fig. B.2, different part of the same arc), thus, we used a narrow redshift prior between 1.8 and 2.4, obtaining a spectroscopic redshift of 2.053. The spectrum of K89.3 shows an H_α emission line, consistent with redshift obtained from [OII] and [OIII] emission lines in the grism spectrum of the same image, shown in Fig. B.2 (the spectral range containing [OII] and [OIII] lines is missing in the NIRSpec spectrum). As the full spectral fit could not produce reliable redshift, we fitted the H_α emission line with a Gaussian profile and obtained the redshift of 3.082 ± 0.008 .

Fig. C.1: 2D and 1D NIRSpec prism spectra of multiple images with previously unknown system redshift. Vertical dashed lines indicate some of the prominent emission lines. The cutouts show the RGB composition of JWST/NIRCam and HST/WFC3 images (F277W, F356W, F410M, F444W in red, F115W, F150W, F200W in green and F814W, F606W, F435W and F090W in blue) with the size of $2''$. Cyan rectangles indicate the MSA slit positions.

Fig. C.2: 2D and 1D NIRSpec prism spectra, not included in Fig. C.1 but also used in this work, either for updating the system redshift (K8a.3), confirming a new multiple image candidate (K62b.3) or for showing the emission line, detected in the grism spectra of the counter images (K33.1).